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Terms and abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DM	Dissemination Manager
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	European Commission
ESCO	Energy Service Company
EM	Exploitation Manager
EU	European Union
EUSEW2020	EU Sustainable Energy Week 2020
GA	Grant Agreement
GAM	General Assembly Meeting
H2020	Horizon 2020
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LI	LinkedIn
PM	Project Manager
PU	Public
QA	Quality Assurance
Q&A	Question & Answer
RE	Restricted
REN	Renewable Energy
SAB	Stakeholder Advisory Board
SC	Steering Committee

SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
SoMe	Social Media
TM	Technical Manager
TSO	Transmission System Operator
TTP	Tech Transfer Programme
TW	Twitter
VP	Vice President
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
YT	YouTube

Executive Summary

The H2020 PLATOON project (“Digital PLatform and analytics TOols for eNergy”) is an EU-financed project that aims to digitalise the energy sector. PLATOON was launched in January 2020 (M1) and was closed in December 2022 (M36). It researched ways to digitalise the energy sector by developing COSMAG-compliant reference architecture for big data processing. The project partners created a digital platform and multiple analytics tools – specifically for the energy sector – that gathered and summarised information from multiple sources (i.e. renewable energy power plants, ESCOs, end users, TSOs, DSOs, etc.), thus helping stakeholders finding and using effectively the most relevant and updated information when being active on the energy market.

The “D9.5 Communication and Dissemination Report III” is the final deliverable of WP9 “Communication and Dissemination” to be delivered in Month 36 (M36). The aim of this deliverable is to provide an insightful report about the communication and dissemination activities of PLATOON during the third and final project year as well as the achievements that have been reached within the given time frame. PLATOON followed a widespread set of dissemination and communication activities in order to communicate the project results to the public, stakeholders, potential users, and experts from the energy industry among others.

Chapter 1 briefly introduces PLATOON and the communication activities that have been made within the third project year. Chapter 2 gives a brief overview of the communication and dissemination strategy, namely the objectives that have been set at the start of the project, the specific target groups as well as the communication and dissemination channels and that have been used to reach various stakeholders. In Chapter 3 there is a detailed monitoring and analysis of the communication and dissemination activities on the website and social media channels, communication and dissemination campaigns, events, open calls,

workshops and training, scientific publications as well as industrial dissemination during the final project year.

Chapter 4 elaborates on the BRIDGE events in which the PLATOON partners took part. Chapter 5 concludes the most important outcomes of the deliverable as well as a summary of the outcomes of the project within the last three years. In Chapter 6, two companies give an internal review about this deliverable. And finally, in Chapter 7, we include some project-related references.

1. Introduction

The aim of “D9.5 Communication & Dissemination Report III” is to report the progress of PLATOON’s “WP9 Communication & Dissemination” during the third and final project year 2022 (M25-M36) to the European Commission (EC). D9.5 is due in December 2022 (M36). D9.5 monitors the overall success of all Communication & Dissemination activities for the third project year as well as the dissemination of the final results of the project overall. The Knowledge and Tech Transfer Department of the Technische Informationsbibliothek Hannover (TIB-KTT) is in charge of **T9.1¹** and **T9.4 of the WP9 Communication & Dissemination** in the scope of the H2020 PLATOON Project.

Overall, it can be stated that WP9's success in the first & second project years could be continued in the third project year of PLATOON as well. The Twitter (TW) and LinkedIn (LI) accounts of the PLATOON project continued to grow steadily, as of 9th of December 2022 (TW: **1150**; LI: **1950**). This means that the accumulated follower number of both TW and LI accounts is now **over 3000**. The PLATOON Partners have visited 25 online and offline events in M25-M36². This means that during the three project years, **over 75** online and offline events have been visited in total. On top of that, another KPI set in the PLATOON GA was already achieved in the second year of the project: **9 PLATOON Press Releases** were published on the project website and were disseminated on the Twitter and LinkedIn project accounts.

Thus, as of December 2022, the WP9 of the H2020 PLATOON project came to a successful end and all major achievements set in the Grant Agreement have been reached.

2. Overview of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy

2.1 Objectives

The goal of WP9 Communication & Dissemination was to organise and execute measures to disseminate and communicate the project and the results it delivered according to the dissemination and communication strategies, defined in D9.1; all with strict alignment to the project’s IPR principles.

¹ Task 9.1 of the PLATOON project has been finalized in M12, as per the GA.

² Out of the 25 events, TIB-KTT has visited 25 events.

The main objectives of WP9 (Task 9.1 and Task 9.4) were:

- Facilitate sharing of knowledge with external, targeted audiences, as well as towards other units of the consortium partners, get feedback from those audiences, and engage them with the project through targeted dissemination activities e.g. presenting at academic and industrial conferences, holding workshops and meetings with developers and engineers, etc.
- Promote visibility of the project and raise awareness about the topics it addresses through effective communication and outreach activities, e.g. publications, the maintenance of the project website, the distribution of printed and electronic material, publication of press releases, etc. The communication and dissemination strategy has been defined in D9.1 in greater detail. It has been refined and continuously improved at both individual-partner and consortium level. The success of the communication and dissemination strategy have been monitored in M12, M24 and M36 (D9.3, D9.4 and this deliverable D9.5).

2.2 Target Groups

Table 1: PLATOON Stakeholder Target Groups

STAKEHOLDER GROUP	BRIEF DESCRIPTION	WHY IS PLATOON INTERESTING TO THEM?	HOW TO ADDRESS THEM
PLATOON Consortium partners	All 20 partners directly involved in the PLATOON project. Wide range of institutions: enterprises, research institutes, public institutions, etc.	PLATOON is of crucial importance to all Consortium partners as it aligns fully with their organisational goals and strategic direction in the domains of digitalisation and the energy sector in particular.	Social Media: YouTube, Twitter, LinkedIn (YT, TW, LI), Printed Media, Newsletters, Live Sessions, Workshops, Trainings, Website, Video Tutorials, Podcasts, PLATOON community on FBA platform.
Energy generation companies/ Energy Service Companies (ESCOs)/ Renewable Energy (REN) Companies	Commercial enterprises that focus on generating electricity, heat, hot water etc., as well as energy services to businesses and private households. Also focus on companies that specialise in renewable energy, green electricity trading and e-mobility.	Should be prepared for emerging big data in the energy sector; links to partners with expertise in Big Data. Operation and maintenance of REN power plants, as well as electricity grids can be improved (e.g. easier to foresee upcoming maintenance work, optimised grids thus longer lifespan of those). The project aims to increase the RE share within the energy sector. By doing so, new REN businesses could be created which is especially good for start-ups and companies with innovative business models.	Fairs/ Exhibitions, Live Sessions, Workshops, Trainings, Newsletters, Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Website, Specific Communication Campaigns, Printed Media, Video Tutorials, Podcasts, PLATOON community on FBA platform.
TSOs/ DSOs	Transmission System Operators and Distribution System Operators that operate and maintain electricity and gas grids; those who provide whole local areas or municipalities with energy.	Should be prepared for emerging big data in the energy sector; links to partners with expertise in Big Data. Critical point of interoperability needed between European energy infrastructures to address global challenges.	Fairs/ Exhibitions, Live Sessions, Workshops, Trainings, Newsletters, Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Website, Specific Communication Campaigns, Printed Media, Video Tutorials, Podcasts, PLATOON community on FBA platform.
Small and medium enterprises	Small and medium-sized	Should be prepared for emerging big data in the	Fairs/ Exhibitions, Social Media (TW, LI, YT),

<p>(SMEs)</p>	<p>companies that focus on a business that is very closely linked to the energy sector; e.g. energy-heavy industries such as the automotive sector, mechanical engineering sector, pharma sector, construction sector etc.</p> <p>Especially those companies that have innovative and future-oriented business models.</p>	<p>energy sector; links to partners with expertise in Big Data.</p> <p>The project aims to increase the REN share within the energy sector. By doing so, new REN businesses could be created, and this could be a chance for industries that could provide these with services, goods, know-how etc.</p>	<p>Website, Specific Communication. Campaigns, Printed Media, Live Sessions, Trainings, Workshops, Video Tutorials, Podcasts, PLATOON community on FBA platform.</p>
<p>Energy End Users/ Building owners</p>	<p>Businesses and private households that consume energy. Also, those households/businesses in focus that possess a REN plant in their homes, or those who want to buy eco power.</p>	<p>Easier access to cheaper, more digitised and sustainable energy, preparing the evolution towards local energy communities.</p> <p>A more decentralised energy system can be created that lowers costs for the energy users and interconnects households with each other (esp. via smart grids); energy security could be improved.</p> <p>Increased energy efficiency for buildings, offices etc. leading to significant cost savings.</p>	<p>Fairs/ Exhibitions, Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Printed Media, Specific Communication Campaigns, PLATOON community on FBA platform.</p>
<p>EU</p>	<p>Political instances of the EC that represent the interests of the European Union.</p>	<p>Increasing the REN share to reach the ambitious 2050 emissions goals.</p> <p>Help to create an inter-European energy grid that is better interconnected and much less dependent on fossil fuels (thus energy supply security on EU-level could be increased).</p> <p>Critical point of interoperability needed between European energy infrastructures to address global challenges.</p>	<p>Newsletters, Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Specific Communication Campaigns.</p>

Municipalities	Cities, settlements or communes that are responsible for certain local/ national/ European areas.	Energy efficiency, optimised energy asset management and social welfare are key priorities of all municipalities and policy makers. Moreover, PLATOON addresses other topics such as smart cities, Local Energy Communities which are highly relevant.	Social Media (YT, LI, TW), Website, Journals, Press releases, Newsletter and Project Communication Material.
Universities and Research centres	Public and private research and educational institutions that focus on providing people with constantly improving and up-to-date knowledge.	The project results/ milestone results are an important input that could enable universities and research centres to exchange knowledge, technology, data etc. and provide other stakeholders with valuable information (f.e. other scientific institutes, companies, etc.).	Social Media (YT, LI, TW), Website, Journals, Specific Communication Campaigns, Printed media, PLATOON community on FBA platform.
General public	All private persons that are generally interested in energy, REN, data science, ecology etc.	The general public, i.e. private persons could be potentially interested in up-to-date energy related topics such as REN, climate change, energy supply security, smart grids, and smart cities a.o. PLATOON addresses the interests of the general public due to the broad range of the topics that the project deals with. Thus, it can engage citizens who are not directly linked to the energy sector to engage themselves into energy topics and become proactive.	Fairs, Social Media (esp. TW, YT), General Communication Campaigns, Printed Media.
Funding agencies	Commercial enterprises and public institutions (f.e. Economic development companies) that are providing start-ups, SMEs and projects on EU level with know-how and financial resources.	Funding agencies focus on state-of-the-art developments in their sector. PLATOON being an innovative project funded by the EC, will make sure to communicate its output to funding agencies in relevant domains.	Fairs/ Exhibitions, Social Media (YT, LI, TW), Website, Specific Communication Campaigns, Live Sessions, Workshops, Trainings, PLATOON community on FBA platform.
Technological Platforms & Professional Associations and	Public platforms that focus on technology-based topics such as	PLATOON implements the digitalisation of the energy sector. Its use cases and pilots are highly relevant to	Journals, Social Media (YT, LI, TW), Website, Newsletters, Live Sessions ⁴ , Workshops,

Initiatives	Big Data, data Science etc. Example: Leibniz-Gemeinschaft.	related platforms and associations in terms of technology transfer, state of the art and lessons learned which can spur further synergies.	Trainings, PLATOON community on FBA platform.
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2.3 Communication Channels and Tools

2.3.1 Website and Social Media

Both the website and the social media channels were the main dissemination tools of the PLATOON project.

The PLATOON website is a cross-cutting online channel which hosts key information, e.g. press releases, blog posts, interviews, a brief project description, a page dedicated to the pilots of PLATOON, an introduction of each PLATOON consortium partner among others.

Social Media (SoMe) channels such as Twitter, LinkedIn or YouTube are used to share experience and participate in conversations about the progress of the project and disseminate project results and outcomes. Here, a simpler language was used in order to attract stakeholders who are less familiar with energy-related or technical topics. Moreover, SoMe such as Twitter and LinkedIn were used to redirect visitors to the website. Also, a PLATOON YouTube channel has been created to disseminate video material of the H2020 energy project.

During the last three years, the PLATOON LinkedIn account generated over **1900** followers, while the PLATOON Twitter account crossed the **1200**-followers-mark.

2.3.2 Online & Offline Events

During the third year of PLATOON, the consortium members visited a broad range of energy events or similar energy-related, technology, sustainability, ecology, innovation, business or climate events. The online events offered an excellent opportunity to participate in relevant energy-related events without being physically present in the event. During these online events, the TIB-KTT department made a great networking effort, i.e. connecting with relevant stakeholders and encouraging them to follow PLATOON on SoMe, just as during the first and second years of the project.

All the visited online and offline events had the focus on the energy sector and were mostly attended by technical stakeholders. However, there were also events on sustainability in a broader sense as well as on digital innovation, digitalisation and technologies related to the digital transformation. These events attracted stakeholders from NGOs, ecological institutions, EU institutions with focus on sustainability as well as ICT companies, technology providers, start-ups and accelerators, among others.

In total, the PLATOON partners visited **25 events**³, both offline and online, from M25 to M36. This means that during the lifetime of the PLATOON, the partners were able to represent the project in **over 75 events**.

³ Out of the 25 visited events from M25-M36, TIB-KTT has visited 20 events.

3. Communication and Dissemination Analysis & Results Monitoring

3.1 Website

The official PLATOON website of the H2020 PLATOON project has been designed to disseminate the project mission, vision, milestones & further info about the project. The structure of the website has been presented in D9.3. Further below are some major updates concerning the PLATOON Website:

- All website pages and subpages have been updated as per the status of December 2022 (in particular, the pilot section)
- The results of Open Call 1 and 2 were displayed in the respective section. The winners of both open calls have been updated & displayed in the “Accelerated SMEs and Start-ups section”
- Update of the section “Supportive Partners”
- Continuous posting of news & blog posts in the “News” section

3.1.1 Website Monitoring

Table 2: PLATOON Website Statistics (M1-M36)

Website Stats	TOTAL (M1-M36)
Visits	17,100
Unique Visitors	11,130
Page Views	56,375
Unique Page Views	39,934
No. published Blog Posts	40
No. published Interviews	12
No. published Press Releases	9 (35 overall translated PRs)

3.1.2 Press Releases

During the third project year (M24-M36), 1 PLATOON Press Releases have been published on the PLATOON website and actively promoted via PLATOON’s SoMe accounts, as well as distributed via the networks of all Consortium partners and CORDIS. As a result, a total of **9 press releases** were published in the past two years and the KPI defined in the GA was already fulfilled at this point. Further below, two examples are shown to demonstrate the promotion of the press releases.

The ninth PLATOON Press Release has been published on the project website in M29 in three different languages of Consortium partners and beyond. **English**⁴, **German**⁵, and **Italian**⁶.

⁴ <https://platoon-project.eu/press-release-the-eu-funded-h2020-project-platoon-selects-7-smes-aiming-to-digitise-the-energy-sector-in-europe-with-disrupting-technologies/>

Figure 1: 9th PLATOON Press Release on the project website

⁵ <https://platoon-project.eu/pressemitteilung-gewinner-des-zweiten-platoon-open-calls/>

⁶ <https://platoon-project.eu/comunicato-stampa-il-progetto-h2020-finanziato-dallue-platoon-seleziona-7-pmi-che-mirano-a-digitalizzare-il-settore-energetico-in-europa-con-tecnologie-dirompenti/>

Figure 2: Promotion of the 9th PLATOON Press Release on the Twitter project account

Figure 3: Promotion of the 9th PLATOON Press Release on the LinkedIn company page

3.2 Social Media

3.2.1 Twitter

Just as during the previous two project year, the PLATOON TW account⁷ has been used to attract the general public that were interested in topics such as energy, sustainability, efficiency, innovation, digitalisation, among others. On top of that, TW has actively been used to attract stakeholders that were directly involved into the energy sector, as well as TW accounts of different DGs of the European Commission. Due to the fact that there was a character restriction for the tweets, the posts on TW were significantly shorter and the language was easier than f.e. on LI.

⁷ https://twitter.com/PLATOON_EU

Figure 4: PLATOON Twitter account as per the 8th of December 2022

3.2.1.1 Twitter Statistics January - June 2022 (M25-M30)

Figure 5: PLATOON Twitter Stats December 2021 (M24) - complete version

Table 3: PLATOON Twitter Stats for the first and second project years 2020 and 2021 (M1-M24)

Twitter Stats	Total (M1-M24 ⁸)
Tweets	523
Impressions	790.1K
Profile Visits	56.38K
Mentions	693
Total Number of Followers	994

Figure 6: PLATOON Twitter Stats January 2022 (M25)

⁸ D9.4 has been submitted in M24. Therefore, D9.5 includes the final stats for M24 and the first & second project years (M1-M24) altogether.

Figure 7: PLATOON Twitter Stats February 2022 (M26)

FEB 2022 SUMMARY

Tweets	Tweet impressions
15	4,714
Profile visits	Mentions
3,950	22
New followers	
13	

Figure 8: PLATOON Twitter Stats March 2022 (M27)

Figure 9: PLATOON Twitter Stats April 2022 (M28)

Figure 10: PLATOON Twitter Stats May 2022 (M29)

Figure 11: PLATOON Twitter Stats June 2022 (M30)

Table 4: PLATOON Twitter Stats M25 - M30 (incl. updated stats for M24)

	M24 ⁹	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30
Tweets	11	9	15	6	17	13	1
Impressions	6,510	4,594	4,714	3,973	10,4	7,030	1,140
Profile Visits	2,777	2,304	3,950	2,436	3,670	2,744	716
Mentions	18	22	22	16	28	21	3
New Followers	3	6	13	22	18	27	6

⁹ Complete Stats for M24, since D9.4 has been submitted on 23.12.2021

3.2.1.2 Twitter Statistics July - December 2022 (M31-M36)

Figure 12: PLATOON Twitter Stats July 2022 (M31)

Figure 13: PLATOON Twitter Stats August 2022 (M32)

Figure 14: PLATOON Twitter Stats September 2022 (M33)

SEP 2022 SUMMARY

Tweets	13	Tweet impressions	3,767
Profile visits	1,839	Mentions	8
New followers	15		

Figure 15: PLATOON Twitter Stats October 2022 (M34)

Figure 16: PLATOON Twitter Stats November 2022 (M35)

Figure 17: PLATOON Twitter Stats December 2022 (M36)

Table 5: PLATOON Twitter Stats M31 - M36

	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
Tweets	0	8	13	1	0	0
Impressions	201	4,549	3,767	528	213	35
Profile Visits	468	1,792	1,839	569	482	95
Mentions	5	2	8	19	13	2
New Followers	4	13	15	5	3	2

Table 6: PLATOON Twitter Stats for the third project year 2022 (M25-M36)

Twitter Stats	Total (M25-M36 ¹⁰)
Tweets	83
Impressions	41.1K
Profile Visits	21K
Mentions	151
Total Number of Followers	132

Table 7: PLATOON Twitter Stats for 2020 - 2022 (M1-M36)

Twitter Stats	Total (M1-M36 ¹¹)
Tweets	606
Impressions	831.2K
Profile Visits	77.4K
Mentions	844
Total Number of Followers	1,139

¹⁰ Status: 8 of December 2022¹¹ Incl. M36 stats as per the 8th of December 2022

3.2.2 LinkedIn

Figure 18: PLATOON LinkedIn company page as per the 8th of December 2022

Table 8: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats for the First and Second Project Years 2020 and 2021 (M1 - M24)

	TOTAL (M1 - M24 ¹²)
Page Views	8,170
Unique Visitors	3,100
Impressions	141K
Unique Impressions	75.3K
Clicks	3,308
Reactions	5,555
Comments	164
Shares	1,256
Engagement Rate	7.59%
New Followers	1,794

¹² D9.4 has been submitted in M24. Therefore, D9.5 includes the final stats for M24 and the first and second project years (M1-M24) altogether.

3.2.2.1 LinkedIn Statistics January - June 2021 (M25 - M30)

Table 9: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats M25 - M30 (incl. updated stats for M24)

	M24 ¹³	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30
VISITORS							
Page Views	210	161	159	122	150	92	38
Unique Visitors	101	71	74	56	65	55	24
UPDATES							
Impressions	8,066	3,353	5,419	3,107	6,610	7,436	919
Unique Impressions	4,658	1,975	3,432	2,082	4,365	4,919	560
Clicks	127	56	67	58	179	163	13
Reactions	290	141	240	167	255	242	22
Comments	9	7	5	1	9	7	0
Shares	15	14	15	9	18	20	4
Engagement Rate	5.47%	6.5%	6.03%	7.56%	6.97%	5.8%	4.4%
FOLLOWERS							
New Followers	42	26	35	12	19	18	5

¹³ Complete Stats for M24, since D9.4 has been submitted on 23.12.2021.

3.2.2.2 LinkedIn Statistics July - December 2021 (M31 - M36)

Table 10: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats M31 - M36

	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36 ¹⁴
VISITORS						
Page Views	22	45	115	114	53	16
Unique Visitors	15	26	66	56	26	9
UPDATES						
Impressions	199	4,097	3,775	1,657	130	63
Unique Impressions	109	2,695	2,596	1,196	65	10
Clicks	5	71	49	375	12	1
Reactions	0	142	169	49	3	1
Comments	0	0	3	0	0	0
Shares	0	23	20	12	0	2
Engagement Rate	2.6%	5.8%	6.2%	21.1%	6.5%	6.3%
FOLLOWERS						
New Followers	3	7	18	10	3	1

¹⁴ Status: Thursday, 8th of December 2022

Table 11: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats for the Third Project Year 2022 (M25 - M36)

	TOTAL (M25 - M36¹⁵)
Page Views	1,087
Unique Visitors	543
Impressions	36,765
Unique Impressions	24,004
Clicks	1,048
Reactions	1,431
Comments	33
Shares	137
Engagement Rate	7.15%
New Followers	157

Table 12: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats for 2020 - 2022 (M1 - M36)

	TOTAL (M1 - M36¹⁶)
Page Views	9,257
Unique Visitors	3,643
Impressions	177.7K
Unique Impressions	99.2K
Clicks	4,357
Reactions	6,986
Comments	196
Shares	1,393
Engagement Rate	7.67%
New Followers	1,945

¹⁵ Status: 8th of December 2022.

¹⁶ Incl. M36 stats as per the 8th of December 2022.

Figure 19: Cumulated Number of PLATOON Followers - LinkedIn & Twitter (M25 – M36)

Figure 20: Cumulated Number of PLATOON Followers - LinkedIn & Twitter (M1 – M36)

3.2.3 YouTube

PLATOON’s YouTube company channel has been used to actively promote the H2020 project. In particular, The ESWC EU Project Networking Session, which has been organized by TIB-KTT in M18 has been actively promoted on the YouTube channel of the PLATOON project. In total, 9 H2020 projects - including PLATOON - had the chance to briefly present their respective projects and to network & connect with the participants afterwards.

Figure 21: PLATOON YouTube Channel as per the 8th of December 2022

3.4 Events

3.4.1 Fairs & Online Conferences

During the third year of the H2020 PLATOON project, the Consortium partners took part in several online fairs and conferences as well as physical events. Several different topics in the sphere of the energy sector such as energy efficiency in buildings and the Renovation Wave, innovative technologies in the renewable energy industry, the emerging hydrogen sector in Europe, the gradual replacement of fossil fuels and fossil energy sources by renewable energy sources within the next decades, among others. Furthermore, the PLATOON partners also visited events with a focus on sustainability and ecology, as well as events on the digitalisation of many different tech industries - including the energy sector.

3.4.2 Overview of the PLATOON Fairs & Online Conferences in 2022 (M25-M36)

Table 13 presents an overview with all **25 events**¹⁷ that the PLATOON partners visited during the third project year (M25-M36).

Table 13: PLATOON Fairs & Online Conferences in 2022 (M25 - M36)

No.	EVENT	DATE	PLACE	DESCRIPTION	WEBSITE	PARTICIPATING PLATOON PARTNERS
1.	Sweden Innovation Days 2022	17 - 20 January	Online	Sweden Innovation Days 2022 was a free four-day, global digital event, dedicated to fostering international collaboration on January 17-20. It focused on what changes need to be made in order to achieve the UN's Global Goals.	https://swedeninnovatiodays.se/	TIB-KTT
2.	FIWARE Smart Fest - Ed. 2	19 - 20 January	Online	Together with its 500+ members and partners, FIWARE Foundation drives the definition — and the Open Source implementation — of key open standards that enable the development of portable and interoperable smart solutions in a faster, easier and affordable way, avoiding vendor lock-in scenarios, whilst also nurturing	https://www.fiware.org/events/fiware-smart-fest-edition-2/	TIB-KTT

¹⁷

				FIWARE as a sustainable and innovation-driven business ecosystem.		
3.	EU-Russia Exchange on Sustainable Building Policies and Measures - Final Conference by BPIE Buildings EU	20 January	Online	The Final Conference of the EU-Russia exchange on sustainable building policies and measures reflects on the entire workshop series that was carried out in 2021, summarise the key takeaways and lessons learned regarding differences and similarities, and foster future collaboration and experience exchange between the key stakeholders.	https://www.bpie.eu/event/final-conference-decarbonisation-of-the-building-stock-in-the-eu-and-russia-the-way-forward/	TIB-KTT
4.	Engaging with Stakeholders to develop energy projects and overcome regulative barriers by the H2020 DECIDE project	26 January	Online	Four initiatives from different European countries including Greece, Spain and Estonia come together to share their experience with stakeholder engagement and how they have linked in with different local, regional and national actors to clear the way to the development of their energy projects and collective actions.	https://decide4energy.eu/events?c=search&uid=i8BvT79w	TIB-KTT
5.	New Year Climate-KIC - Let's celebrate our Entrepreneurship Programmes	27 January	Online	During the New Year Climate-KIC event, the celebration of the EIT Climate-KIC Entrepreneurship Programmes is done by sharing information, insights, best practices and future prospects for 2022. It is a great occasion for the entire community of stakeholders to get together. Citizens, students, experts, corporates, governments, entrepreneurs and partners have the opportunity to connect with EIT Climate KIC's global ecosystem of breakthrough solutions in emissions reduction and climate adaptation.	https://www.eventbrite.com/e/new-year-climate-kic-lets-celebrate-our-entrepreneurship-programmes-registration-227547880837?keep_tld=1	TIB-KTT
6.	Media Data Space	31 January	Online	The objective of the Digital European Platform of	https://platoon-	TIB-KTT

	Workshop			Quality Content Providers is to support the creation of a European Data Space dedicated to the Media sector.	project.eu/platoon-at-the-media-data-space-workshop/	
7.	NGI Explorers' Awards Ceremony	2 February	Online	The NGI Explorer program is coming to an end and the consortium has decided to treat the community of bright minds and exceptional individuals that have made the program so successful to a unique event, meant to celebrate the amazing results achieved together: the NGI Explorers Oscars. Each of the Explorers is asked to pitch their project in a brief demo session, to showcase their results and project highlights, divided by core technology cluster.	https://explorers.ngi.eu/agenda-oscars	TIB-KTT
8.	DAPSI Final Event	2 February	Online	The Final DAPSI Event #2 displays the latest innovative solutions in the area of data portability.	https://app.livestorm.co/cap-digital-1/dapsi-final-event-2	TIB-KTT
9.	EU Industry Days 2022	8 - 11 February	Online	The EU Industry Days is Europe's flagship annual event, highlighting industrial frontrunners, ongoing industrial policy discussions and improving the knowledge base of European industry. It is the main platform to discuss industry challenges and co-develop opportunities and policy responses in an inclusive dialogue with a wide range of stakeholders.	https://eu-industry-days.ec.europa.eu/	TIB-KTT
10.	IDSA Winterdays 2022	16 - 17 February	Online	The theme of IDSA Winterdays 2022 is trust. The IDS reference architecture puts trust at its core. IDS connectors are designed for trust-based data sharing. IDS certification confirms the trustworthiness of components and operating environments. Use cases and data spaces show how trust is turned into value.	https://internationaldata-spaces.org/events/idsa-winterdays-2022/	TIB-KTT
11.	Prosumers as the Future of Energy	17 February	Online	The H2020 project MERLON opens conversation with H2020 Renaissance project and H2020 INTERPRETER project to discuss energy in local communities and	https://www.eventbrite.es/e/prosumers-as-the-future-of-energy-	TIB-KTT

				flexibility in grids management	registration-251419391167	
12.	EUHubs4Data EUH4D 2022 - Building a Trusted and Fair Data-Driven Federation	29 March	Online	Data Forum 2022 examines the creation of a federation of Data-Driven Innovation Hubs from the law and ethics perspective. It outlines the current and upcoming regulatory landscape and its impact on cross-border data-driven innovation and experimentation. The event welcomes entrepreneurs and SMEs creating data and AI services, DIHs wanting to strengthen their ecosystem, ethics and law scholars analysing the effects of the regulation, policy-makers and experts shaping the environment or anyone curious to see how the future of European innovation is shaped.	https://euhubs4data.eu/data-forum-22/	TIB-KTT
13.	Smart Cities Marketplace Forum 2022	26 - 27 April	Online & in Brussels	The Smart Cities Marketplace Forum 2022 is organised in collaboration with the Covenant of Mayors Office and the European Innovation Council and the Netherlands Enterprise Agency, among others partners, and will include a welcome and opening keynote by the European Commissioner for Energy, Kadri Simson. Participants are able to network and build capacity, exchange knowledge on the clean energy transition, funding and financing opportunities, and learn how to improve citizens' quality of life by integrating innovative and clean-technology solutions in Europe.	https://commission.europa.eu/events/smart-cities-marketplace-forum-towards-just-and-clean-urban-transition-2022-04-26_en	TIB-KTT
14.	The Knowledge Graph Conference 2022	6 - 9 May	New York City & online	The Knowledge Graph Conference (KGC) 2022 is a 5 day hybrid conference with multiple parallel tracks everyday, covering a multitude of topics related to knowledge graph technologies. It offers a great variety of subject matter related to knowledge graphs (KG) and knowledge technologies.	https://www.knowledgegraph.tech/kgc-2022/	PUPIN

15.	BDVA/DAIRO DataWeek 22 - Towards an innovative, trusted and fair European data economy	24 May - 9 June	Online	Data Week is gathering of the European Big Data and Data Driven AI research and innovation communities. In Data Week, the participants share knowledge and results, discuss topics of common interest, find synergies, build new collaborations and identify new challenges and recommendations. Data Week also links the communities and their results to the European policies and market needs and brings European initiatives and activities closer to local communities.	https://www.big-data-value.eu/data-week-2022/	TIB-KTT
16.	Hannover Messe 2022	30 May - 2 June	Online	HANNOVER MESSE is be the world's first major industrial event. Its focus on digitalization and sustainability stimulates innovative and efficient approaches to production and climate protection.	https://www.hannovermesse.de/en/news/news-articles/hannover-messe-2022-rescheduled-for-beginning-of-june	TIB-KTT
17.	Panel Discussion on Data ecosystems, as part of the forthcoming First International Workshop on Data Ecosystems in conjunction with 48th International Conference on Very Large Data Bases (VLDB) Conferences 2022	5 - 9 September	Sydney & online	VLDB is a premier annual international forum for data management, scalable data science and database researchers, vendors, practitioners, application developers, and users. The VLDB 2022 conference features more than 250 research talks, eleven keynote & invited talks, two panels, nine tutorials, over 40 demonstrations, and 10 workshops, including the VLDB PhD Workshop. It covers issues in data management, database architectures, graph data management, data privacy and security, data mining, machine learning, AI and database systems research - all essential technological cornerstones of the emerging applications of the 21st century.	https://vldb.org/2022/ https://dbis.rwth-aachen.de/DEco22/	PUPIN
18.	PCI Energy Days 2022	19 - 20 September	Online	The PCI Energy Days provides project promoters the opportunity to showcase their PCI projects and share	https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/infrastructure	TIB-KTT

				their experience to further develop the EU's energy infrastructure.	/projects-common-interest/pci-energy-days_en	
19.	European Sustainable Energy Week 2022	26 - 30 September	Online	The European Sustainable Energy Week brings together public authorities, private companies, NGOs and consumers to promote initiatives to going green and digital for Europe's energy transition. Under the theme "Going green and digital for Europe's energy transition the main topics include REPowerEU, the digitalisation and integration of energy systems, energy efficiency, renewables, consumers and a fair energy transition, decarbonisation policies and international cooperation.	https://european-sustainable-energy-week.b2match.io/	TIB-KTT
20.	European Research & Innovation Days 2022	28 - 29 September	Online	European Research and Innovation Days is the European Commission's annual flagship Research and Innovation event, bringing together policymakers, researchers, entrepreneurs and the public to debate and shape the future of research and innovation in Europe and beyond.	https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/events/upcoming-events/research-innovation-days	TIB-KTT
21.	PLATOON General Assembly in Bilbao	6 - 7 October	Bilbao	General Assembly in Bilbao organized by the PLATOON partners. The Consortium members are discussing the final steps to conclude the H2020 project this year in December 2022.	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6985228483027202048 https://twitter.com/PLATOON_EU/status/1579429339506290688	all
22.	SINERGY Open Event on "Smart and Innovative eENERGY management",	16 November	Belgrad	Face to face event with participants from Serbia, Austria, Ireland, North Macedonia, Bosnia and Herzegovina.	https://project-sinergy.org/3rd-Open-Event	PUPIN

	collocated with the TELFOR'22 Conference					
23.	European Big Data Value Forum 2022	21 - 23 November	Prague	The European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) brings together industry professionals, business developers, researchers and policy-makers from all over Europe and other regions of the world to advance policy actions, and industrial and research activities in the areas of Data and AI.	https://european-big-data-value-forum.eu/	TIB-KTT
24.	IEEE Open Event on MODERN POWER SYSTEM TECHNOLOGIES – TOWARDS A SUSTAINABLE ENERGY FUTURE	23 November	Vienna & online	Face to face event with participants from Serbia & Austria.	https://project-sinergy.org/node/153	PUPIN
25.	ENLIT Europe 2022	29 November - 1 December	Frankfurt am Main	Enlit is a constantly growing, inclusive and end-to-end forum that addresses every aspect of the energy agenda. A community that for 365-days a year collaborates and innovates to solve the most pressing issues in energy.	https://www.enlit-europe.com/	TECN

3.5 Open Calls (FBA)

During the final year of the PLATOON project no open calls were running, therefore, no dissemination activities related to open calls per se were performed. However, both support programmes were active during the final year of the projects.

Several dissemination activities were performed by FBA to create visibility for the project by showcasing the results of the beneficiaries that were participating in the support programmes, as well as to demonstrate the impact of the cascade funding initiative on the project. The following two activities were performed:

- Interviews in a media outlet, Sustain Europe;
- Attending The Business Booster event.

See further details below.

Sustain Europe

Sustain Europe is a semi-annual magazine and [website](#) that is well-known within the European sustainable energy ecosystem and is promoting responsible solutions to ensure long term climate protection, see examples of the magazine in Figure 22 below.

Figure 22: Sustain Europe magazine editions

The dissemination in Sustain Europe included online interviews with 13 beneficiaries (see Figure 23 below), as well as several pages in the magazine dedicated to PLATOON, including an interview with PLATOON's Technical Coordinator, Erik Maqueda (see Figure 24 below).

The purpose of this dissemination activity was to reach a broad audience and to boost the visibility of PLATOON, as well as to demonstrate the success of the support programmes, the value that the support programmes generated for PLATOON and for the society in general by boosting the development of digital innovations for the sake of a sustainable future.

Figure 23: Example of two interviews with beneficiaries

Figure 24: Extract from the magazine displaying the pages dedicated to PLATOON

The Business Booster

The Business Booster is an annual two-day international networking event that showcases 150+ sustainable energy technologies under one roof and is organised by EIT InnoEnergy. This event was held between 28-29 September in Lisbon, Portugal. From PLATOON’s side, the following partners participated: FBA and ROM, as well as three beneficiaries of the first support programme who had successfully developed components of the PLATOON reference architecture. Images from the event are below.

Figure 25: PLATOON in the event catalogue (left); One of the PLATOON beneficiaries being interviewed (right).

Figure 26: One of the PLATOON beneficiaries pitching their project on stage.

Figure 27: PLATOON’s Booth

The event was a success and it attracted several investors, companies as well as SMEs to PLATOON’s booth. These innovators showed high interest in PLATOON’s end-result and they will become potential end-users of the PLATOON marketplace. This demonstrated that what PLATOON is creating is valuable to the sustainable energy ecosystem and demonstrated the importance of cascade funding to help contribute to the technology transfer into the market.

3.6 Ambassadors (FBA)

The Ambassadors selected for PLATOON were Nathalie Mitton, Jad Nassar and Thorsten Huelsmann. Their profiles are described on the PLATOON’s [website](#) and the screenshot is available in the figure below.

Figure 28: Profiles of the Ambassadors

Name	Photo	About the Ambassador
Thorsten Huelsmann		<p>Thorsten Huelsmann is CEO of Digital Hub Logistics and Digital Hub Management GmbH located in Dortmund since 2010. In 2016 he was additionally appointed as Head of Unit Strategic Initiatives at Fraunhofer Institute of Material Flow and Logistics IML and as CFO of International Data Spaces Association IDSA.</p> <p>He holds a Master in Economic Geography, Sociology and Political Sciences from University of Bonn and studied Communication Sciences at University of Bologna.</p> <p>Mr Huelsmann focuses his work on the management and coordination of innovation networks, initiatives and clusters. He uses stakeholder engagement and qualitative research methods as well as strategic foresight tools.</p> <p>In 2019 Digital Hub Logistics was awarded as the winner of the DIHNET.EU award, in 2010 Digital Hub Logistics was awarded as the winner of the leading-edge cluster competition of the German government.</p>
Nathalie Mitton		<p>Dr. Nathalie Mitton received her MSc and Ph.D. degrees in Computer Science from INSA Lyon in 2003 and 2006 respectively. She received her Habilitation à diriger des Recherches (HDR) in 2011 from Université Lille 1.</p> <p>Since 2006, Dr. Mitton has been an Inria full researcher and since 2012, she is the Scientific Head of the Inria FUN team which is focused on small computing devices like electronic tags and sensor networks. Her research interests focus on self-organization from PHY to routing for wireless constrained dynamic and mobile networks with a strong focus on energy.</p> <p>Dr. Mitton has been nominated as one of the 10 Women Stars in Computer Science in 2020 by the IEEE Communication Society. She has published her research in more than 40 international reviews and more than 120 international conferences. Dr. Mitton is involved in the set-up of the FIT IoT LAB platform, the H2020 CyberSANE projects, and in several program and organization committees such as Infocom (since 2019), PerCom (since 2018), DCOSS (since 2018), Adhocnow (since 2015), ICC (since 2015), Globecom (since 2017), Pe-Wasun 2017, VTC (since 2016), etc. She supervises several Ph.D. students and engineers.</p>
Jad Nassar		<p>Dr Jad Nassar is an Assistant Professor in Computer Science at Junia-HEI. He has a PhD in Computer Science specialized in Internet of Things (IoT) applied to Smart Grids. He teaches in the field of Computer Science and IoT. Dr Nassar’s research interests include communication and data acquisition in smart devices and wireless networks for different applications such as Smart Grids, Smart Cities, etc. Dr Nassar is currently working on several European projects in the area of Smart Grids such as EBalance+ and SoMel SoConnected.</p>

The majority of dissemination actions performed by the ambassadors happened during the course of the open calls, however, the ambassadors continued to create awareness for PLATOON through their digital channels, see examples in the figure below.

Figure 29: Re-tweets about PLATOON

Building on their long career in the field of energy, PLATOON Ambassadors also wrote and published 12 scientific articles in the community about Smart Grids, Energy Data Sharing and European Data Spaces, see examples of the articles below.

Figure 30: Articles by the ambassadors

3.7 Supportive Partners Programme (FBA)

The Supportive Partners' Programme for communities involves entities from across Europe, such as start-up communities, accelerators, governments, programmes and more to help PLATOON to empower innovation and entrepreneurship in the crossroads of ICT and energy and connect the ecosystem. The Supportive Partners are stakeholders interested in disseminating the project in a win-win cooperation mode. These are identified via community mapping, starting from the PLATOON partners' networks. The list of Supportive Partners is presented in the table below.

Table 14: List of the PLATOON Supportive Partners (updates)

No.	Name	Country	Brief Description	Website
1	Big Data Value Association (BDVA)	Belgium	The Big Data Value Association (BDVA) is an industry-driven international not-for-profit organisation with more than 200 members all over Europe and a well-balanced composition of large, small, and medium-sized industries as well as research and user organizations.	https://www.bdva.eu/
2	BerriUp Aceleradora de Startups	Spain	BerriUp Aceleradora de Startups is the first private startup accelerator in the Basque Country. The Donostia-based company, founded in 2015, seeks to support entrepreneurs in launching their projects on the market by accompanying them in the process of validating the business, collaborating with institutional initiatives in the public sector.	https://www.berriup.com/
3	EIT InnoEnergy	Netherlands	EIT InnoEnergy is the leading engine for innovation and entrepreneurship in sustainable energy, across Europe and beyond.	https://www.innoenergy.com/
4	Stara Zagora Regional Economic Development Agency, SZ REDA	Bulgaria	The main objective of SZ REDA is to support the development and implementation of mechanisms to manage the process of successful integration into the European community of local and regional authorities and businesses in the region through policy development at a regional and local level aimed at sustainable development and stimulating economic development.	https://szeda.eu/en/
5	Tenerrdis Energy Cluster	France	Tenerrdis Energy Cluster supports sustainable economic growth in the new energy technology industries and coordinates a network spanning industry, government, academia, and scientific	https://www.tenerrdis.fr/en/

			research to address the challenges of the energy transition.	
6	Vestbee	Poland	Vestbee is the biggest online matchmaking platform for startups and scaleups in Central & Eastern Europe supported by the global community of VC funds, corporates, business angels and accelerators such as Amazon, HubSpot, InnoEnergy, Engie, Credo Ventures, Next Road Ventures, Tera Ventures, EIT Digital or SABIC.	https://www.vestbee.com/
7	WeSmart	Belgium	WeSmart is a Belgium scale-up founded by specialists with a long experience in the energy and environment sector that has developed a digital platform “as a service” to fully manage energy communities.	http://www.wesmart.com/en
8.	Enagas	Spain	Enagas is a Spanish energy company and European transmission system operator (TSO), which owns and operates the nation’s gas grid. The firm also owns four liquefied natural gas regasification terminals in the country, at Huelva, Barcelona, Cartagena, and Gijon.	https://www.enagas.es/portalsite/enagas
9.	REENGEN	Turkey	REENGEN is a high-tech company established in 2013. Reengen’s Energy IoT Platform is a cloud based PaaS data analytics solution for commercial buildings, industrial facilities and renewable energy plants.	http://www.reengen.com/
10.	International Data Spaces Association	Germany	The International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) is a coalition of more than 130 member companies that share a vision of a world where all companies self-determine usage rules and realize the full value of their data in secure, trusted, equal partnerships; and we are making that vision a reality. The aim of IDSA is a global standard for international data spaces (IDS) and interfaces, as well as fostering the related technologies and business models that will drive the data economy of the future across industries.	https://internationaldataspaces.org/
11.	Elblox AG	Switzerland	Elblox AG develops and runs digital energy transaction platforms that are used for delivering renewable energy from producers directly to consumers. Elblox AG creates a new customer experience for energy by tracing energy back to its source, visualization of energy flows, monitoring consumption and/or generation, and providing tools to manage cost or invoices in real-time.	https://www.elblox.com/
12.	ASBA Foundation	Armenia	The National Social Housing Association (ASBA) was established in Armenia as a result of Dutch-Armenian Cooperation. Its aims are to develop social housing stock; to become a social entrepreneur by applying sound business principles in developing and managing social housing to achieve their social goals; to attract capital for the social rental stock; to introduce	http://www.asba.am/

			innovative sustainable management of new and existing housing; to manage the social housing stock independently, professionally and cost-efficiently; to make a profit on management and commercial activities related to housing in order to reinvest in social housing development.	
13.	ENLINE Transmission	Portugal	ENLINE Transmission is the brand name of GML's technology and software solutions. ENLINE provides an innovative Digital Twin sensor-less technology with advanced analytic and diagnostic algorithms to exploit the untapped potential of your transmission assets.	https://www.enline-transmission.com/
14.	SPRI Group	Spain / Basque Country	SPRI Group works with companies to facilitate access to digitalisation, cybersecurity and helps to set up companies. SPRI helps to look at the best way of expanding one's business in other countries or to look for physical spaces, pavilions, or offices where customers can set up their companies. SPRI has resources to face any challenge and a global vision that helps to lead the way.	https://www.spri.eus/en/
15.	Inwebit	Poland	Inwebit is a technology partner in digital transformation. Started as a custom software development company Inwebit evolved to business-oriented, aware of the specifics of the industry, product development experts with a broad spectrum of competencies to solve the right problem with the right solution. Inwebit has its own, highly innovative R&D lab, with very talented and experienced engineers, which gave Inwebit the opportunity to not only develop a software part of one's product but to build a product as a whole, with all the electronics and all the integrations that customers need.	https://inwebit.pl/pl/start
16.	Revolve Media	Belgium	REVOLVE MEDIA is dedicated to communicating about water, energy, ecosystems, mobility, and the circular economy. We provide communication support to EU-funded projects and work closely with strategic partners to advance their sustainability projects.	https://revolve.media/
17.	TechnologyCatalogue.com	Netherlands	Discover and deploy technological innovations to accelerate energy transition. That's the objective of TechnologyCatalogue.com. With over 700 technologies and 70,000 unique users of the platform, TechnologyCatalogue.com supports the energy transition by providing a platform that bridges the gap between technology suppliers, end-users and experts, and facilitates technological innovations towards a more sustainable energy sector.	https://www.technologycatalogue.com/
18.	Enermaps	Switzerland	EnerMaps Open Data Management Tool aims to improve data management and accessibility in the field of energy research for the renewable energy industry. EnerMaps' tool accelerates and facilitates the energy transition offering a qualitative and user-friendly digital platform to energy professionals.	https://enermaps.eu/

19.	Smart Energy DIH	Lithuania	The Digital Innovation Hub brings together major research, business and public stakeholders in Lithuania for the common development and implementation of digital transformations in the renewable energy, greenhouse gas reduction, eco-design, recycling, environmental protection, circular business model development and associated sectors that meet European citizens' needs.	https://smartenergydih.eu/
20.	I-ENERGY (an EU-funded initiative)	Greece	EU funded initiative, aiming to support and develop new AI-based Energy Services. I-ENERGY aims at evolving, scaling up and demonstrating innovative AI-as-a-Service (AlaaS) Energy Analytics Applications and digital twins services that will be validated along 9 pilots.	https://i-nergy.eu

3.8 Mentoring Committee (FBA)

The Mentoring Committee is composed of Technical Mentors, who provide technical mentoring to the third-party projects. Each third-party project was assigned a dedicated Technical Mentor with whom the project members collaborate throughout the support programme. The performance of each project was evaluated by the Mentoring Committee after each milestone. The evaluation criteria were the following:

- Deliverables' quality.
- Technical performance indicators.
- Deadline Compliance.

Members of the Mentoring Committee for both support programmes are shown in the table below.

Table 15: List of Mentors

Mentor's name	Beneficiary	Support Programme
Valentina Janev	PLATOON-01	First Support Programme
Jose Barriga	PLATOON-02	First Support Programme
Patrick Maurelli	PLATOON-03	First Support Programme
Marco Mussetta	PLATOON-04	First Support Programme
Martino Maggio	PLATOON-05	First Support Programme
Philippe Calvez and Erik Maqueda	PLATOON-06	First Support Programme
Valentina Janev	PLATOON-07	Second Support Programme
Erik Maqueda	PLATOON-08	Second Support Programm
Marco Musetta	PLATOON-09	Second Support Programm
Luis Garcia	PLATOON-10	Second Support Programm
Patrick Maurelli	PLATOON-11	Second Support Programm
Philippe Calvez and Marco Musetta	PLATOON-12	Second Support Programm
Pau J. Cortes	PLATOON-13	Second Support Programm

3.9 Industrial Dissemination (CEPV)

According to the PLATOON Dissemination and Communication Strategy defined in the deliverable D9.1, the industrial dissemination activities in the scope of Task 9.3 are specifically addressed to the following target segments of the energy value chains:

- Developers and/or owners of energy assets
- O&M service providers
- Wind turbine Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs, Tier 1)

- Equipment and components manufacturers (Tier 2 and 3)
- ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) companies
- Research and development centers - testing facilities

In order to reach relevant companies from these target segments, PLATOON partners have kept on carrying out a number of dissemination activities during the last project year (2022), which are reported in the following subsections.

Fortunately, most of the industrial dissemination and communication activities planned in 2022 have been carried out in close to normal conditions, in particular those events involving physical attendance and large gatherings such as exhibitions and conferences. A great effort has been made this year to disseminate the project outcomes in face-to-face events, focusing specially on the pilots' deployment and validation.

3.9.1 Participation in relevant exhibitions, events and conferences of the energy sector

Exhibitions, conferences and large face-to-face events have been successfully recovered in close to normal conditions in 2022, especially after the first quarter of the year. PLATOON industrial dissemination team made the most of this opportunity to improve the project visibility and disseminate its results at European level.

Participation in Wind Europe annual event – Conference & Exhibition (Bilbao, April 5-7th, 2022)

The Wind Europe annual event (<https://windeurope.org/annual2022/>) Conference & Exhibition, was held on 5-7 April in Bilbao, being one of the main events for wind energy worldwide in 2022.

PLATOON was disseminated at the “Wind Energy Basque Country” booth, arranged by CEPV, with special focus on the Wind Farm predictive maintenance use case led by VUB. Fifty Basque companies and entities from the wind energy value chain were exhibiting at the booth, TECN among them.

During the 3-day exhibition, project dissemination materials were displayed at the booth and meetings with interested stakeholders in the Wind energy use case were held, with participation from TECN and CEPV.

Figure 31: PLATOON at Wind Europe annual event 2022

Participation in XVII International Electric Equipment Conference (JIEEC) (Bilbao, May 10-11th, 2022)

JIEEC (<https://jieec.com/en/>) is a biannual conference organized by TECN, which aims to promote a meeting forum in which experts and researchers from different countries and fields can exchange ideas and discuss the state of the art and the progress in the electricity grids, considering that they are the backbone of the energy system and a key element in ensuring an efficient energy transition. In 2022 edition, the event paid special attention to the role of the technologies and their impact on the European Green Deal and on the NextGenerationEU program.

The programme included a presentation on *“Interoperable and Trusted Common Data Spaces for the Energy sector: from H2020 PLATOON project to GAIA-X Energy Data Space”* by Philippe Calvez (ENGIE), which covered the basic concepts of the project and a particular focus on the Predictive maintenance for Wind turbines use case.

Figure 32: PLATOON at JIEEC 2022

Participation in the IoT Week (Dublin, June 20-23rd, 2022)

The 11th edition of IoT Week (<https://iotweek.org/iot-week-2022-dublin/>) was held in Dublin, from 20 to 23 June 2022, chaired by MANDAT INT.

The conference activities enabled participants to thoroughly explore the status of Internet of things technologies, applications, and challenges ahead, including a contribution of IoT solutions to the UN’s sustainability goals. The comprehensive program included around 115 sessions, workshops, panel discussions, a Hackathon, a Startup Competition, and 5th edition of the Global IoT Summit.

CEPV received an invitation from the European Commission (Rolf Riemenschneider, DG CNECT) to participate in a session on *“Data spaces: Common data models for Energy, Home, Mobility”*. As a result, a PLATOON presentation (available [at this link](#)) was made on Jun 22nd by Erik Maqueda (TECN). Representatives from other projects and initiatives such as OPEN DEI, FIWARE, INTERCONNECT and BRIDGE also took part in the session.

After the presentations, a round table was held in which the panellists discussed around the requirements and obstacles of data models for energy, home and mobility.

Figure 33: PLATOON at IoT Week 2022

Agenda:

10 minutes	EC Introduction	Rolf Riemenschneider, DG CNECT, EC
50 minutes	Pitches on approaches to “Energy Data Spaces”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OPEN DEI: Alberto Dognini (RWTH Aachen) • PLATOON: Erik Maqueda (Tecnalia) • Juan José Hierro (FIWARE) • INTERCONNECT: Laura Daniele (TNO) • BRIDGE: Olivier Genest (Trialog) • Henrik Madsen (DTU)
30 minutes	Round table on “Requirements and obstacles of data models for energy, home and mobility”	<p>Moderator: EC or OPEN DEI</p> <p>Panelists: pitches presenters</p>

Participation in Wind Energy Hamburg Conference & Exhibition (September 27-30th, 2022)

Wind Energy Hamburg Conference & Exhibition 2022 took place on 27-30 September and was another major event for the wind energy sector, covering both onshore and offshore domains.

PLATOON was disseminated at the “Wind Energy Basque Country” booth, arranged by CEPV. Seventeen Basque companies and entities from the wind energy value chain exhibiting at the booth.

Figure 34: PLATOON at Wind Energy Hamburg Conference & Exhibition 2022

Participation in ENLIT Europe 2022 (Frankfurt, November 29th-December 1st, 2022)

Enlit Europe 2022 (<https://www.enlit-europe.com>) - the new unifying brand for European Utility Week & POWERGEN Europe – was held on Nov 29 – Dec 1 in Frankfurt, being the main European event focused on the energy transition.

In the framework of PLATOON Industrial Dissemination activities, the Basque Energy Cluster (CEPV) booked a stand for PLATOON in the [European projects zone](#) (stand: 12.0.C10-35), a pavilion aimed to disseminate research and findings of EU projects. An updated project roll-up focused on the pilots, brochures, a video on a Digital Twin of a Wind Turbine Power Train made by TECN and a pilots’ booklet specifically designed and printed out for the purpose were displayed at the booth. CEPV team oversaw the booth during the whole event with support from TECN, PUPIN and ENGIE, answering questions and explaining the project details to the visitors.

Figure 35: PLATOON Booth at the European Projects Zone (ENLIT Europe 2022) - Part 1

Figure 36: PLATOON Team at the European Projects Zone (ENLIT Europe 2022) - Part 2

PLATOON was also disseminated at the Basque Country Pavilion (poster and brochure printouts), coordinated by CEPV and focused on the Basque Smart Grids value chain, involving companies and entities such as TECN, PLATOON Technical Coordinator. An updated PLATOON poster focused on the pilots was displayed at one of the walls and pilots' booklet printouts were delivered to interested visitors.

Figure 37: PLATOON dissemination at the Basque Country Pavilion (ENLIT Europe 2022)

Figure 38: PLATOON pilots' booklet

Dissemination on the project pilots and outcomes was also made through a presentation at the European Projects' Hub by Erik Maqueda (TECN), particularly focused on the Predictive Maintenance of LV-MV Distribution Transformers use case, since it was considered the one that best fits the scope of ENLIT event.

Figure 39: PLATOON presentation at EU Projects' Hub (ENLIT Europe 2022)

The participation at ENLIT event was disseminated through CEPV channels and social networks.

Figure 40: Dissemination of PLATOON activities at ENLIT Europe 2022 in social media

3.9.2 Periodic contacts and launch of collaboration initiatives with selected entities and stakeholders

OPEN DEI initiative (<https://www.opendei.eu/>)

Collaboration and involvement of PLATOON in OPEN DEI initiative has continued during 2022, aiming to facilitate interaction, mutual knowledge and exchange of best practices and results between a number of projects specifically focused in providing added value to energy stakeholders through efficient data handling, processing and analysis.

CEPV has continued co-chairing the WG3 on Linking Ecosystems on behalf of PLATOON, in close cooperation with OPEN DEI management team and with support from the H2020 projects involved, looking to facilitate knowledge sharing, exploit dissemination and promote joint activities to make an efficient use of their allocated resources.

Follow-up meetings of WG3 have been organized and held in Jan 27th, Feb 24th, Apr 24th and May 20th, chaired by CEPV and OPEN DEI teams, with participation from the projects involved in the WG and representatives from the European Commission (DG CONNECT).

The main actions carried out in this framework during the reporting period have been the following:

- Projects and pilots' presentations in the meetings (knowledge exchange)
- Details on PLATOON Open Calls' results and lessons learnt provided to other OPEN DEI projects.
- Organization of joint dissemination events:
 - Joint Open Call dissemination webinar on March 17th, 2022, chaired by the EC (DG CONNECT) to share knowledge with European SMEs and start-ups on the ongoing projects from the Open Calls already held and identify opportunities in coming Open Calls. PLATOON 1st Open Calls winners Barbara IoT and MiPU Energy Data were invited by CEPV to share their experience and the projects progress (further details provided in chapter 3.9.3).
 - Workshop on "Knowledge Sharing on Business models for Digital Platforms in Energy domain: Best Practices by PLATOON project" (Apr 21st, 2022). Online workshop aimed at sharing the knowledge and lessons learnt by PLATOON in terms of business modelling methodology and marketplace for energy platforms with other companies (mainly SMEs) on their way towards data exploitation. Presentation by Fernando Merino (Indra-Minsait) (further details provided in chapter 3.9.3).

o Other activities promoted by OPEN DEI:

- Contribution to OPEN DEI Business Impact survey by Juan Prieto (Indra-Minsait)
- Contribution to OPEN DEI Open Calls analysis by Diana Järve (FBA)

Industrial Data Space Association (IDSA) (<https://internationaldataspaces.org/>)

PLATOON contributed to the Industrial Data Space Association (IDSA) Data Spaces Discovery Day (<https://internationaldataspaces.org/data-spaces-discovery-day-barcelona/>), held in Barcelona on Sep 28th, 2022, with TECN among the co-organizers.

A specific workshop on "*How to implement IDS with focus on energy data spaces*" was organized, particularly focused on the Wind Energy use case with participation from TECN (Erik Maqueda, Alberto Berreteaga) and CEPV (Begoña Molinete).

Figure 41: Dissemination at IDSA Data Spaces Discovery Day

3.9.3 Organisation of workshops and conferences, targeted to industrial European audiences

Workshop on “Best Practices for Energy Data Sharing” (Feb 16th, 2022, online)

The workshop was promoted by the European Commission in the framework of the Digitalisation of the Energy System Action Plan (DoEAP), with the aim of sharing basic principles and best practices for establishing a European Energy Data Space, which is built on common rules compliant with industrial and economic interests and also with the legal framework

J.I. Hormaeche (CEPV) was invited by Rolf Riemenschneider (DG CNECT) to present PLATOON as a European initiative in the energy data sharing domain, together with other three panellists.

After the presentations, the panellists exchanged their views on several topics such as the most relevant components in a standardised data framework, how to keep the balance between centralized and distributed data processing, the role of public and private stakeholders to foster an innovative marketplace for energy services and how to scale up the lessons learnt from ongoing initiatives at a European level.

All the details about the workshop are available [at this link](#), as well as the [session recording](#).

Figure 42: Workshop snapshot and agenda excerpt

Panel 2	<i>Evidence from national/European initiatives</i>		Panelists:
4	50 min	<p>11:00 – 11:50</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>What are key elements of a common/standardized data framework?</i> • <i>What balance would you see between local data and centralised data collection and storage? For example, data processed in control centers or through local aggregation/control (e.g. at building or district level)?</i> • <i>What role do private or public actors play in driving the market for innovative energy services ?</i> • <i>What lessons learned from existing initiatives could/should be scaled up to a European level?</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Henrik Madson, DTU (DK) • José I. Hormaeche, Basque Energy Cluster, (ES) • Lars Meindert, Ministry of Economic Affairs & Climate (NL) • Ursula Tauschek, Oestereichs Energie (AT) <p>Moderated by Valerie Reif, European University Institute</p>

Open Call joint dissemination webinar on March 17th, 2022

This event was organized in the framework of the OPEN DEI WG3 and chaired by the EC (DG CONNECT) to share knowledge with European energy stakeholders (mainly SMEs and start-ups) on the ongoing projects from the Open Calls already held and identify opportunities in the coming Open Calls. The announcement and the details for the event are available [at this link](#).

After an introductory presentation by the European Commission (Svetoslav Mihaylov, DG CONNECT) about the Open Calls, their role, and their importance in European Projects, the webinar was split into two sessions.

In the first panel, presentations on the running and upcoming Open Calls were given by representatives from EU projects Synergy, InterConnect and BD4NRG. Details on the requirements, scope of the call, eligibility terms, timeline and funding were given for each call.

Later on, a second panel took place in which four beneficiaries from the past Open Calls held by Interface and PLATOON projects shared their experiences and lessons learnt. PLATOON

1st Open Calls winners Barbara IoT and MiPU Energy Data were invited by CEPV to participate in this panel.

The event was concluded with a Q&A session and some closing remarks by the chairpersons.

Figure 43: Open Call Joint dissemination event announcement and agenda

Agenda

Title	Time	Speaker
European commission introductory presentation	10.00 - 10.10	Svetoslav Mihaylov (European Commission – DG CNECT)
Presentation of running and upcoming Open Calls	10.10 - 10.40	Speakers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ugo Stecchi (Grupo Etra – Synergy project) • Raquel Carro (FundingBox – InterConnect project) • Maria Papadimitriou (Cintech Solutions - BD4NRG project)
Beneficiaries experiences and results	10.40 - 11.40	Speakers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interrface beneficiary • Laurent Schmitt (Digital4Grids - Interrface project) • Peter Rawlins and Miren Zabaleta (Barbara IoT- PLATOON project) • Giuseppe Pirrelli (MiPU Energy Data - PLATOON project)
Q&A session	11.40- 12.00	

Workshop on “Knowledge Sharing on Business models for Digital Platforms in Energy domain: Best Practices by PLATOON project” (Apr 21st, 2022)

This online workshop was organized in the framework of the OPEN DEI WG3, aimed at sharing the knowledge and lessons learnt by PLATOON in terms of business modelling methodology and marketplace for energy platforms with other companies (mainly SMEs) on their way towards data exploitation. The announcement and the details for the event are available [at this link](#).

The workshop was chaired by Golboo Pourabdollahian, from IDC. After an introduction on OPEN DEI initiative by Giorgio Micheletti (IDC) and an overview on the Energy digital platforms by Alberto Dognini (RWTH Aachen), a presentation was given by Fernando Merino (Indra-Minsait), explaining more in detail the business model methodology and the PLATOON marketplace.

The event was concluded with a Q&A session and some closing remarks by the chairpersons.

Figure 44: Workshop announcement and agenda

Agenda

Title	Time	Speaker
Welcome and Introduction to the session	11.30 - 11.35	Golboo Pourabdollahian, IDC
Introduction of OPEN DEI	11.35 – 11.40	Giorgio Micheletti, IDC
Overview of Energy digital platforms	11.40 – 11.50	Alberto Dognini, RWTH
Business model methodology and PLATOON marketplace	11.50 – 12.20	Fernando Merino Blanco, Indra-Minsait
Interactive session	12.30 – 12.45	All
Wrap-up and Closing remarks	12.45 – 12.50	Golboo Pourabdollahian, IDC

Workshop on “PLATOON Digital Business Models for the Energy Sector” (Bilbao, Oct 5th, 2022)

This event was co-located to the last General Assembly of the project and aimed to disseminate the business model methodology developed in PLATOON, highlight some of the most relevant use cases where it has been applied and collect feedback from Basque companies and stakeholders in the energy sector, mostly focused on wind energy and smart grids fields.

It was promoted by CEPV with strong support and commitment from Indra-Minsait, TECN, SAM and ENGIE and gathered together 18 representatives from 10 entities, who discussed with PLATOON team around the opportunities that the exploitation of operation data from wind farms and distribution grids.

The workshop took place on the 5th of October at TECN facilities and was moderated by CEPV, which presented its objectives, the contents to be addressed and the participating speakers. Erik Maqueda (TECN), Technical Coordinator, then briefly introduced the project, its technical foundations and the 7 pilots in which the technologies developed are being validated.

In the central part of the session, Fernando Merino and Eduardo Jiménez, from Indra Minsait, explained the methodology they have developed for the definition of business models focused on the digitalisation of the energy sector, based on the Osterwalder/Pigneur "value proposition and business model canvases" and illustrated with some examples. They

also presented the evolution of these business models towards the definition of both specific and joint exploitation plans, as is the case of the PLATOON Marketplace, a solution for the exchange of data, services and tools between owners, suppliers and users of energy data based on the IDS (International Data Spaces) architecture.

In addition, the application of this methodology to a series of specific use cases in the wind power and electricity grids sectors, developed by ENGIE/TECN and SAM respectively, was demonstrated. Erik Maqueda (TECN) presented two business models for the valorisation of operating data in the wind sector involving different actors in the value chain: data sharing by wind farm owners and wind turbine manufacturers (OEMs) to component manufacturers (TIER2-3) for product improvement; and retail of Digital Services by component manufacturers (TIER2-3) to wind farm owners, wind turbine manufacturers (OEMs) and operation and maintenance (O&M) companies. Pau Cortés (SAM) presented the analysis carried out for two business cases in the field of electricity distribution: the optimisation of MV/LV transformers maintenance by applying Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques and the detection of non-technical losses using AI algorithms.

After the presentations, a space for debate was opened, in which attendees provided their comments and points of view on the business cases analysed and where the complexity of the interrelationships between the various actors involved (energy infrastructure owners, OEMs, electrical/wind component manufacturers, maintenance operators...etc.) and the need to identify value propositions with clear benefits that satisfy all parties was highlighted.

Figure 45: Workshop on PLATOON Business Models

3.10 Scientific Dissemination (TIB-SDM)

This section reports the results of the activities conducted by the PLATOON consortium to disseminate the project outcomes in scientific venues. They include five articles in international journals, ten publications in the proceedings of international conferences, two in proceedings of a Ph.D. consortium, and eight presentations at international events. Additionally, one of the papers received the best research paper award, published in high-ranked venues, e.g., CIKM, the International Conference on Logic Programming, the Journal of Web Semantics, and the Journal of Physics, Energies, and Renewable Energies. The outcomes of the research activities are summarized in the following subsections.

3.10.1 Scientific Publications

Journal Articles

In this reporting period, the partners of the PLATOON consortium have published five journal papers. Figures 46 and 47 present the abstract of these articles. The paper entitled “Responsible Knowledge Management in Energy Data Ecosystems” outlines the challenges of Data Ecosystems in the Energy sector and proposes an approach to combine data and knowledge to enhance the analytics services portfolio of various energy stakeholders. Knowledge graphs are positioned as flexible data structures for integrating the convergence of data and knowledge from the energy domain. Architecture for creating a knowledge graph for renewable energy data sources is presented. Analytical tasks, e.g., wind power production forecasting, are implemented on the knowledge graph. Additionally, the article shows how data integration provides the basis for developing techniques for transforming top-down, centralized production and rigid distribution framework into a collaborative ecosystem of self-managed prosumers able to act independently on the liberalized energy markets. The article is published in Energies in the Special Issue of Advances in Disruptive Business Models in the Energy Sector. It is persistently identified and openly accessible.

The papers entitled “Scaling up knowledge graph creation to large and heterogeneous data sources” and “Efficient semantics summary graphs for querying large knowledge graphs”, tackle the problems of scalability of the data integration process and query processing. Since the time complexity of both tasks depends on the size and number of data sources that are integrated or queried, the proposed methods are paramount in the energy sector, where data sources are usually large and heterogeneous. The paper on “Scaling up knowledge graph creation to large and heterogeneous data sources” is published at the Journal of Web Semantics in the Special Issue of Automated Knowledge Base Construction, Volume 75, January 2023. The paper on “Efficient semantics summary graphs for querying large knowledge graphs” is published in the Volume 2, Issue 1, April 2022 of the International Journal of Information Management Data Insights; it is openly accessible.

Figure 46: Publications in International Journals Reporting Data Management Techniques for Enhancing Scalability of Knowledge Graph Creation and Query Processing

The two articles whose abstracts are depicted in Figure 47 address the problems of anomaly detection and fault detection in wind turbines, and present machine learning methods to effectively address these problems. The article entitled “The detection of generator bearing failures on wind turbines using machine learning based anomaly detection” is openly accessible of the Journal of Physics: Conference Series 2022. Finally, the paper on “A deep boosted transfer learning method for wind turbine gearbox fault detection” is part of the volume 197, September 2022 of the Journal of Renewable Energy.

Figure 47: Publications in International Journals Reporting Machine Learning Techniques for Anomaly Detection in Turbines

Publications in Proceedings of International Conferences and Workshops

Ten articles are published in the proceedings of international conferences and two in proceedings of Ph.D. doctoral consortium; Table 16 depicts the bibliographic information of these publications. The published articles address various topics, which range from techniques for data integration, similarity computation, anomaly detection, ethical issues on knowledge graphs, and analytical methods. Figure 48 shows the certificate for best paper award received by the partners of the consortium in their paper entitled “Towards a Solution for an Energy Knowledge Graph”. It proposes knowledge graphs built by a semantic-driven architecture, and puts in perspective that relevance of knowledge graphs in energy related analytical tasks.

Table 16: Description of the Articles Published in the Proceedings of International Conferences and Workshops

Conference Name	Year	Title Contributor	Authors	PLATOON Partner
KGSWC-2022 Fourth Ibero-American Knowledge Graph and Semantic Web Conference joint with Third Indo-American Knowledge Graph and Semantic Web Conference	2022	Semantic data models construction in the H2020 PLATOON project	Dr. Sarra BEN ABBES and Dr. Lynda TEMAL	ENGIE
SAC'22 - The 37th ACM/SIGAPP Symposium on Applied Computing	2022	EABlock: A Declarative Entity Alignment Block for Knowledge Graph Creation Pipelines	Samaneh Jozashoori, Ahmad Sakor, Enrique Iglesias, Maria-Esther Vidal	TIB
IEEE Fifth International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Knowledge Engineering (AIKE)	2022	Ethical and Sustainability Considerations for Knowledge Graph based Machine Learning	Carsten Felix Draschner, Hajira Jabeen, Jens Lehman	UBO

IEEE International Conference on SEMANTIC COMPUTING (ICSC)	2022	DistAD - A Distributed Generic Anomaly Detection Framework over Large KGs	Farshad Bakhshandegan Moghaddam, Jens Lehmann, Hajira Jabeen	UBO
IEEE Fifth International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Knowledge Engineering (AIKE)	2022	SimE4KG - Explainable Distributed multi-modal Semantic Similarity Estimation for Knowledge Graphs	Carsten Felix Draschner, Hajira Jabeen, Jens Lehman	UBO
Semantic-Intelligence Conference ISIC 2022	2022	Towards a Solution for an Energy Knowledge Graph	Dušan Popadić, Enrique Iglesias, Ahmad Sakor, Valentina Janev and Maria-Esther Vidal	PUPIN / TIB
Wind Europe Electric City 2021 Copenhagen	2021	Data Analytics Tools and Hybrid Digital Twin for Wind Turbines	Ainhoa Pujana / Jan Helsen	TECN / VUB
PLATOON - OPENDEI - Conference: Data sharing and governance for Energy applications	2021	Technological challenges in data sharing for energy applications	Erik Maqueda	TECN
CIKM '21: Proceedings of the 30th ACM International Conference on Information & Knowledge Management	2021	DistRDF2ML - Scalable Distributed In-Memory Machine Learning Pipelines for RDF Knowledge Graphs	Draschner, Carsten & Stadler, Claus & Bakhshandegan Moghaddam, Farshad & Lehmann, Jens & Jabeen, Hajira	UBO
Proceedings of the Annual Conference of PHM Society 2021	2021	Condition Monitoring of Wind Turbines and Extraction of Healthy Training Data Using and Ensemble of Advanced Statistical Anomaly Detection Models	Xavier Chesterman, Timothy Verstraeten, Pieter-Jan Daems, Ann Nowé, Jan Helsen	VUB

2021 IEEE 15th International Conference on Semantic Computing (ICSC)	2021	DistSim - Scalable Distributed in-Memory Semantic Similarity Estimation for RDF Knowledge Graphs	Draschner, Carsten & Lehmann, Jens & Jabeen, Hajira	UBO
LAMBDA Big Data Analytics Summer School. Doctoral Workshop, 2021	2021	Semantic Analytics in the Palm of your Browser	Draschner, Carsten & Bakhshandegan Moghaddam, Farshad & Lehmann, Jens & Jabeen, Hajira	UBO
LAMBDA Big Data Analytics Summer School. Doctoral Workshop, 2021	2021	Semantic Web Analysis with Flavor of Micro-Services	Bakhshandegan Moghaddam, Farshad & Draschner, Carsten & Lehmann, Jens & Jabeen, Hajira	UBO
SEMANTiCS Conference 2021	2021	Literal2Feature: An Automatic Scalable RDF Graph Feature Extractor	Bakhshandegan Moghaddam, Farshad & Draschner, Carsten & Lehmann, Jens & Jabeen, Hajira	UBO
International Conference on Logic Programming	2021	Geolog: Scalable Logic Programming on Spatial Data	Tobias Grubenmann and Jens Lehmann	UBO

Figure 48: Best Paper Award on “Towards a Solution for an Energy Knowledge Graph”

Presentations in Conferences

Fifteen articles were presented at scientific conferences; the consortium partners highlighted the effect of the presented approaches in efficiently and effectively resolving problems in the energy sector. An exemplary talk is the one summarized in Figure 49. In this speech, the partners of ENGIE presented the PLATOON semantic data models to the scientific community on Semantic Web. The talk put into perspective the critical role these models play in semantic data integration and data harmonization in work packages 2 and 5, respectively.

Figure 49: Industrial Talk on “Semantic data models construction in the H2020 PLATOON project” at the fourth edition of the Iberoamerican conference KGSWC 2022 and the third edition of the Indo-American Conference KGSWC 2022. Madrid, Spain. November 21-23, 2022

Industry Talk 1

Title: Semantic data models construction in the H2020 PLATOON project

Speakers: Dr. Sarra BEN ABBES and Dr. Lynda TEMAL, CSAI Lab ENGIE, France

Abstract: During the last few years, the electricity sector is experiencing its most dramatic transformation since its creation. Nowadays, electricity covers almost 20% of global energy consumption and it is expected to rise exponentially during the following decades both in absolute and relative terms. In fact, according to the World Energy Outlook for 2018 published by the International Energy Agency (IEA), electric power demand could rise 90% from today to 2040. At the same time, the digitization of the energy sector is rapidly increasing through the roll-out of sensors and IoT platforms in all the components of the energy network that capture vast amounts of data. Likewise, there are also new computing capabilities available that allow exploiting the value of data, and converting information into knowledge. In this sector, data exchange and data integration between stakeholders become mandatory to develop innovative smart services and use cases. Therefore, semantic interoperability represents a key challenge, in dealing with very heterogeneous Energy platforms that differ in terms of technologies, communications protocols, and data models. In this talk, Sarra BEN ABBES and Lynda TEMAL from CSAI Lab ENGIE (France) will present a specific methodology to create harmonized semantic data models that include all the needs of use cases, done in the context of the H2020 PLATOON project (<https://platoon-project.eu/>).

Logos at the bottom: CCS, Springer, CEUR Workshop Proceedings, Open Research Knowledge Graph, DBpedia.

3.10.2 Scientific Workshops and Summer Schools

In addition to the presentations conducted at international conferences (see Table 17), the partners of PLATOON have participated in seven scientific events. Table 17 describes these contributions. These scientific events have different natures, ranging from a webinar on digital transformation to a research workshop to knowledge graphs for data integration. In all the events, the partners of PLATOON have put into perspective the challenges that impose the management of Big data in the energy sector. More importantly, they discussed with the respective community the open problems and grand challenges that still need to be achieved.

Table 17: Participation in Scientific Events

Event Type	Event Name	Venue	Date	Title Contribution	Authors	PLATOON Partners
Webinar	IEEE IAS/PELS/IES Austria Chapter Digital Transformation Technology Webinar	Online	25.11.2021	Integrated Energy Value Chains	Valentina Janev	PUPIN
Conference	ESWC 2022. Project Networking	Onsite	01.06.2022	PLATOON (Digital PLATform and analytic TOOLS for eEnergy)	Maria-Esther Vidal	TIB
Workshop	DEco 2022. VLDB Conference	Hybrid	05.09.2022	Panel Discussion	Valentina Janev and Maria-Esther Vidal	PUPIN and TIB
Conference	9th International Symposium on Applied Computing for Software and Smart systems (ACSS-2022)	Online	10.09.2022	Semantic Intelligence in Energy Management Systems	Valentina Janev and Maria-Esther Vidal	PUPIN and TIB
Stakeholders Thematic Open	Smart Grid Technology	Onsite	02.06.2022	Semantic Interoperability in Smart	Valentina Janev	PUPIN

Event	underpinning Sustainable and Secure Energy in Europe			Grid Scenarios		
Congress	Building Digital Twin International Congress	Online	25.05.2022	Managing Knowledge in Energy Data Spaces	Valentina Janev	PUPIN
Workshop	Knowledge Graphs for Data Integration	Onsite	30.11.2022	Knowledge Graph: Are We Ready to Catch the Boat?	Maria-Esther Vidal	TIB

PLATOON was presented in the Project Networking track of the Extended Semantic Web Conference (ESWC 2022). This event was held onsite in Greece on May 29-June 2, 2022. Fourteen European projects were presented in this track. The presentation of the main challenges addressed in these projects provided the basis for fruitful discussions with the track participants. Figure 50 depicts the information about PLATOON on the track website.

Figure 50: Description of the talk of PLATOON in the Project Networking Track held at ESWC 2022, May 29-June 2, 2022

Project Networking

The following projects were accepted to and participated in the ESWC 2022 Projects Networking Session:

PLATOON (Digital PLATform and analytic TOOlS for eNergy)
 Website: <https://platoon-project.eu/>
 Contact: maria.vidal@tib.eu

PLATOON is an EU-funded H2020 project that aims to digitalize the energy sector, enabling thus data exchange while ensuring privacy and sovereignty. PLATOON knowledge graphs integrate energy data sources in terms of the common understanding of the energy domain stated by the PLATOON Semantic Data Models. The PLATOON framework is validated in seven pilots from four countries.

The First International Workshop on Data Ecosystems (DEco'22) was conducted on September 5, 2022 in conjunction with the 48th International Conference on Very Large Databases. DEco'22 aimed at publishing contribution to the problems of data integration and analytics, and the relevant role of data ecosystems. The workshop was organized by Cinzia Cappiello (Politecnico di Milano, Milan, Italy), Sandra Geisler (RWTH Aachen University, Aachen, Germany), and Maria-Esther Vidal (TIB and Leibniz University of Hannover, Hannover, Germany). As part of an exciting agenda, a panel on data ecosystems was conducted. The discussion covered interesting experiences of the participants in the health and energy domain. The panel included outstanding experts of the field, namely Ernestina Menasalvas (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid), Paolo Missier (Newcastle University), and Barbara Pernici (Politecnico di Milano), and the PLATOON partner Valentina Janev (The Mihajlo Pupin Institute). The event was hybrid and participated more than 30 persons onsite and 40 online. Figure 51 shows pictures taken during the discussion with the panellists.

Figure 51: Panel on Challenges on Data Ecosystems in Healthcare and Energy. In the context of Deco- First International Workshop on Data Ecosystems in Conjunction with VLDB 2022

On November 30th, 2022, the PLATOON partner Maria-Esther Vidal, gave the keynote talk at the Knowledge Graphs for Data Integration event held in Leuven, Belgium. This event was conducted in the context of the FWO Scientific Research Network Kick-Off. In her talk entitled: “Knowledge Graphs- Are We Ready to Catch the Boat?”, Maria-Esther Vidal discussed with the community the challenges of data management that have been faced in the tools for knowledge graph creation and federated query processing. The application of these techniques in the context of PLATOON were also presented to the community. Figure 52 presents a picture of one of the scalability issues addressed in Work Packages 2 and 5.

Figure 52: Invited Talk on “Knowledge Graphs- Are We Ready to Catch the Boat?” at Knowledge Graphs for Data Integration- FWO Scientific Research Network Kick-Off

3.10.3 Additional Scientific Achievements

The techniques developed in Work Packages 2 and 5 have been used in pilot 2a to integrate RES data sources into a knowledge graph. The results of this work not only received the award presented in Figure 53, but also was awarded by the European Commission's Innovation Radar. The innovation title is “A dedicated Knowledge Graph for integration of RES data sources” and the partners TIB and PUPIN are recognized as “Key Innovators” by the commission. The information about the innovation is publicly available on the commission website. Figure 50 presents a screenshot of the innovation. This portal highlights the role of these approaches in the context of PLATOON. More importantly, this award puts in perspective the relevance of this innovation in the context of Big data solutions for energy.

Figure 53: Panel on Challenges on Data Ecosystems in Healthcare and Energy. In the context of Deco- First International Workshop on Data Ecosystems in Conjunction with VLDB 2022

3.11 Communication & Dissemination KPIs for 2022 (M25-M26)

Table 18: Comm & Diss KPIs for 2022 (M1-M36) - Reference Values & Actual Values

KPIs	REFERENCE VALUES	ACTUAL VALUES (M36)
Project Website	10,000 visits	> 17,000 visits
Leaflets, Posters	> 10 national / international events	24

Press Releases	> 8 press releases by end of the project	9 (35 overall translated PRs)
Social Media	1,000 followers on Twitter by end of the project 15,000 impressions	> 1,140 followers on Twitter > 1,940 followers on LinkedIn 20,000 impressions per month on average (M1-M36)
Meetings & Workshops	> 20 events	70

To conclude this chapter, the highlights of the WP9 KPIs achieved in the second year of the PLATOON project are briefly described below. Table 18 shows the KPIs that were set at the beginning of the PLATOON project as well as the actual values as per M36. Further below in Figure 54, the key highlights of the PLATOON comm & diss achievements for the period M1-M36 are shown.

In the course of the last three years, the PLATOON **Twitter** account acquired **over 1150 followers** while the PLATOON **LinkedIn** account gained **over 1940 followers**. As stated in the previous D9.3, these are outstanding results, given the fact that other H2020 energy project accounts that have existed for a longer period of time than PLATOON could only generate a smaller number of followers both on Twitter and LinkedIn. With the release of **9 PLATOON press releases**, another major KPI could be achieved during the second project year. A total of 35 different versions were released in 9 different European languages¹⁸. As per M36, the PLATOON partners have visited a total of **over 75 events**, both online and offline, of which 20 were visited by the TIB-KTT department. Just like during the previous year, all events were either energy- or digitalisation-related, or covered similar topics that were compatible with PLATOON such as sustainability, climate action, and innovative technologies, among others.

To sum up, from a communication and dissemination perspective, the third PLATOON project year (M25-M36) proved to be just as fruitful as the previous two years, and WP9 as a whole yielded excellent results.

¹⁸ The languages were: English, German, French, Spanish, Italian, Portuguese, Russian, Serbian, and Dutch.

Figure 54: Highlights – Final PLATOON KPIs in 2020/21/22 (M1-M36)

4. Assessing the Impact of the COVID-19 Outbreak

The PLATOON Consortium is updated as per all the measures of the EC with relation to the ongoing EU-funded projects and this topic is discussed regularly at the level of the Steering Committee, aiming to mitigate potential negative impacts for the project. Although there were some physical events (in correspondence with the continuously updating security measures with regards to the COVID 19 pandemic) where PLATOON has been presented, the vast majority of the events were online. TIB, as WPL9, facilitated this process in 2021 by offering online alternatives and will continue it in the next project year, e.g. by proposing to the partners the organisation of live sessions in which they can present the PLATOON project.

To counteract the COVID implications, the TIB-KTT team has been intensively active via social media and during online events and conferences, succeeding thus in implementing impactful outreach and project promotion across related and relevant stakeholders.

5. Conclusion

In summary, the third and last project year (M25-M36) has been very fruitful and successful for WP9 and its Tasks.

The PLATOON project was able to further expand its established community and already high numbers of followers on both Twitter and LinkedIn, thus attracting more stakeholders from the energy sector and beyond. Just as during the previous two project years, the WP9

Lead and WP9 Deputy worked increasingly online in order to adapt to the ongoing COVID19 situation. Therefore, most of the visited and organised events took place online and the online events remained the key for the expansion of the PLATOON Community.

Overall, despite the ongoing consequences from the ongoing COVID 19 pandemic, the TIB-KTT Division as well as FBA, CEPV and the TIB-SDM Division can report very large success for T9.2, T9.3, and T9.4. The PLATOON Partners achieved a successful finalisation of the project in the third and last project year 2022 (M25-M36). It is expected that the PLATOON website will be hosted by ENGIE while TIB-KTT will manage the social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube) of PLATOON for the next 2 years after the official project end.